

Horizon 2020 Societal Challenge 5:
*Climate action, environment,
resource efficiency and raw materials*

CONSTRAIN

CONSTRAIN: 'Constraining uncertainty of multi-decadal climate projections'

GA number 820829
H2020-LC-CLA-2018-2

More information: cordis.europa.eu/project/id/820829
Project archive: zenodo.org/communities/constrain-project-820829

Work Package: WP5

Deliverable number: WP5.12

Deliverable title: Online interactive infographics created such as the Climate Action Tracker, but targeting both adaptation and mitigation decisions

Short summary:

- CONSTRAIN has worked with the Climate Change Tracker (<https://climatechangetracker.org/>) to develop a platform hosting a range of publicly available climate data. Although primarily aimed at policymakers involved in UNFCCC negotiations, this aims to provide a range of audiences with a reliable, user-friendly means of tracking and understanding climate change and its progression, placing several updated IPCC-consistent indicators of climate change in the public domain.
- The dashboard initially focuses on three key indicator sets: greenhouse gas emissions, human-induced global warming, and the remaining global carbon budget, bringing together and presenting up-to-date information crucial to effective climate decision-making in a findable, accessible, traceable and reproducible way.
- The dashboard provides further information on each indicator and also provides standardised application programming interfaces (APIs) and charts to embed in third-party apps and websites. In time, and with feedback from the user community, the initial set of indicators displayed by the dashboard may be expanded to include others alongside their rates of change.
- Further work by CONSTRAIN, in partnership with Carbon Brief, is also producing infographics aimed at sharing understanding of how different emissions pathways will affect our chances of staying within 1.5°C global warming. We expect this to be completed in time for the COP28 summit.
- See: <https://climatechangetracker.org/igcc>

Cite as:

Schleussner C. 2023. Climate Change Tracker. The CONSTRAIN Project. Available at:
<https://climatechangetracker.org/igcc>.